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A MATHEMATICAL MODEL IN RESTRICTED THREE-BODY PROBLEM WHEN THE SMALLER PRIMARY IS A UNIFORM STRAIGHT ROD

Muhammad Amjad¹, Mohd. Aslam² and Mohd. Kashif Khan³

Department of Mathematics

Al-Falah University, Faridabad (Haryana)–121004, India

¹E-mail:amjadmsctech@gmail.com

²E-mail:kidwaiaslam@gmail.com

³E-mail:md.kashifkhan85@gmail.com

Abstract

In this paper we have shown the existence of libration points in the restricted three-body problem when the smaller primary is a uniform straight rod. It is found that there exist five libration points out of which L_i ($i=1, 2, 3$) are collinear and $L_{4,5}$ are non-collinear. The collinear libration points are unstable for $0 \leq \mu \leq \frac{1}{2}$ and $0 < l < 1$ while non-collinear libration points are stable for critical value of mass parameter $\mu_c = 0.381410285\dots$ and length parameter $l_c = 0.4$.

Key Words: Celestial Mechanics, Restricted three-body problem, Collinear Libration points, Non-collinear Libration Points, Stability of Libration points.

1. Introduction

In celestial mechanics, restricted three-body problem is a world known problem in which two finite bodies called primaries move around their center of mass in circular or elliptic orbits under the influence of their mutual gravitational attraction and a third body of infinitesimal mass is moving in the plane of the primaries which is attracted by the primaries and influenced by their motion but not influencing them. In classical case there exist five libration points out of which three are collinear and two are non-collinear. The collinear libration points L_1 , L_2 and L_3 are unstable for $0 \leq \mu \leq \frac{1}{2}$ and the non collinear libration points $L_{4,5}$ are stable for a critical value of mass parameter $\mu < \mu_c = 0.03852\dots$, Szehebely (1967).

Restricted three-body problem has been studied by many scientists and mathematicians. Rodica and Vasile (2006) have analyzed the restricted three-body problem in Schwarzschild's gravitational field. They have discussed the existence of the equilibrium points in the orbital plane and established the corresponding positions. Raheem and Singh (2006) have investigated the stability of equilibrium points under the influence of small perturbations in the coriolis and centrifugal forces, together with the effects of oblateness and radiation pressures of the primaries. They have found that the collinear points remain unstable while the triangular points are stable for $0 \leq \mu \leq \mu_c$ and $\mu_c \leq \mu \leq \frac{1}{2}$, where μ_c is the critical mass parameter depends upon the coriolis force, centrifugal force, oblateness and radiation pressure of the primaries. Jagdish Singh et.al (2010) have investigated the stability of equilibrium points in the restricted three-body problem, in which the masses of the luminous primaries vary isotropically in accordance with the unified Meshcherskii law, and their motion takes place within the framework of the Meshcherskii problem. They observed that collinear and coplanar points are unstable, while the triangular points are conditionally stable. Elshaboury and Mostafa (2011) gave some stability conditions of L_4 in the restricted

three-body problem when the smaller primary and the infinitesimal body are oblate spheroids. E. I. Abouelmagd and M. A. Sharaf (2012) have discussed the existence of libration points and their linear stability when the more massive primary is radiating and the smaller is an oblate spheroid. They observed that the collinear points remain unstable while the triangular points are stable for $0 \leq \mu \leq \mu_c$, and unstable in the range $\mu_c \leq \mu \leq 1/2$, where $0 < \mu_c < 1/2$. They also found the relations for periodic orbits around five libration points with their semimajor, semiminor axes, eccentricities, the frequencies of orbits and periods. E. I. Abouelmagd (2012) proved that the locations of the triangular points and their linear stability are affected by the oblateness of the more massive primary in the planar circular restricted three-body problem. After that, he has shown that the triangular points are stable for $0 < \mu < \mu_c$ and unstable when $\mu_c \leq \mu \leq 1/2$, where μ_c is the critical mass parameter which depends on the coefficients of oblateness. He also gave some numerical values for the positions of the triangular points, μ and μ_c using planets systems in our solar system. Idrisi and Taqvi (2013) have studied the existence and stability of the libration points in the restricted three-body problem when the smaller primary is an ellipsoid. They have determined the equations of motion of the infinitesimal mass which involves elliptic integrals and then they have investigated the collinear and non-collinear libration points and their stability in linear sense and found that there exist five collinear libration points and the non-collinear libration points are lying on the arc of the unit circle whose centre is the bigger primary and shown that the libration points either collinear or non-collinear all are unstable. Idrisi and Taqvi (2014) have discussed the existence and stability of the non-collinear libration points in the restricted three-body problem when both primaries are ellipsoids. They have found that the non-collinear libration points exist only in the interval $52^\circ < \varphi < 90^\circ$, formed an isosceles triangle with the primaries and all the non-collinear libration points were unstable in their study. Narayan and Singh (2014) have studied the motion and orbital stability of the infinitesimal mass in the vicinity of the equilateral lagrangian points of the elliptic restricted three body problem, considering photo gravitational effects of both the primaries. They have studied the stability of the triangular points under the effects of radiating primaries around the binary system.

In this paper we have considered the smaller primary as a uniform straight rod of length $2l$ and the bigger one a point mass. Our aim is to investigate the equations of motion of the infinitesimal mass m_3 , the collinear and non-collinear libration points and their stability in linear sense. There are five sections in this paper. In section 2, the equations of motion of the infinitesimal mass m_3 have been determined. In section 3, location of collinear and non-collinear libration points have been investigated. In section 4, the stability of collinear and non-collinear libration points have been checked. In last section, we have discussed all the results.

2. Equations of motion

Fig. 1: The Configuration of the RTBP when one primary with mass M is a uniform straight rod

Let M be a uniform straight rod of length $2l$ and m_1 a point mass ($m_1 > M$). They are moving in the circular orbits around their center of mass O . An infinitesimal mass m having the co-ordinates (x, y) at a point P is moving in the plane of motion of m_1 and M . The distances of the infinitesimal mass m from m_1 , M and O are r_1 , r_2 and R respectively. We wish to find the equations of motion of m using the terminology of Szehebely (1967), in synodic system and dimensionless variables.

Let AB be a uniform straight rod of length $2l$ and $P(x, y)$ be any point at which we have to find the potential of the rod. The potential of the rod at $P(x, y)$ is given by (Ramsey, 1959),

Fig. 2: Potential of a uniform straight rod at an external point $P(x, y)$

$$V = M \log \frac{r + r' + 2l}{r + r' - 2l} \tag{1}$$

where M = mass of the rod,

$2l$ = length of the rod,

$PB = r'$ and $PA = r$.

The potential of the rod in our case is therefore given by,

$$V = \mu \log \frac{r + r' + 2l}{r + r' - 2l} \tag{2}$$

where $\mu = \frac{M}{m_1 + M} \leq \frac{1}{2}$, $m_1 + M = 1$.

2.1 The equations of motion of m in the synodic system and dimensionless variables are:

$$\ddot{x} - 2n\dot{y} = \Omega_x, \tag{3}$$

$$\ddot{y} + 2n\dot{x} = \Omega_y. \tag{4}$$

The integral analogous to Jacobi integral is

$$(\dot{x}^2 + \dot{y}^2) = v^2 = 2\Omega - C \tag{5}$$

where

$$\Omega = \frac{n^2}{2} (x^2 + y^2) + \frac{1-\mu}{r_1} + V$$

V is defined in the Equation (2),

$$\Omega_x = n^2 x - \frac{1-\mu}{r_1^3} (x-\mu) - \frac{4\mu l}{(r+r')^2 - 4l^2} \left(\frac{x+1-\mu+l}{r} + \frac{x+1-\mu-l}{r'} \right),$$

$$\Omega_y = n^2 y - \frac{1-\mu}{r_1^3} y - \frac{4\mu l}{(r+r')^2 - 4l^2} \left(\frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{r'} \right) y,$$

$$r_1 = \sqrt{(x-\mu)^2 + y^2},$$

$$r = \sqrt{(x+1-\mu+l)^2 + y^2},$$

$$r' = \sqrt{(x+1-\mu-l)^2 + y^2},$$

V is the velocity of m ,

C is the constant of integration

and n is the mean-motion of the primaries given by

$$n = \sqrt{\frac{2l}{1-l^2}}, \quad 0 < l < 1.$$

(6)

Fig. 3: l verses n

From the Fig. 3 this is observed that as l increases in the interval $0 < l < 1$, the mean-motion of the primaries also increases. For $l = 0.4$ the mean-motion of the primaries is unity.

3. Libration Points

At the libration points

$$\dot{x} = 0, \dot{y} = 0, \ddot{x} = 0, \ddot{y} = 0.$$

Therefore, equations of motion become

$$\Omega_x = n^2 x - \frac{1-\mu}{r_1^3} (x-\mu) - \frac{4\mu l}{(r+r')^2 - 4l^2} \left(\frac{x+1-\mu+l}{r} + \frac{x+1-\mu-l}{r'} \right) = 0, \tag{7}$$

$$\Omega_y = n^2 y - \frac{1-\mu}{r_1^3} y - \frac{4\mu l}{(r+r')^2 - 4l^2} \left(\frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{r'} \right) y = 0. \tag{8}$$

3.1 Collinear Libration Points

Collinear libration points are the solution of the equations $\Omega x = 0$ and $y = 0$ i.e.

$$n^2 x - \frac{1-\mu}{(x-\mu)^2} - \frac{2\mu l}{(x+1-\mu)^2 - l^2} = 0, \tag{9}$$

On simplifying the Equation (9), we have

$$n^2 x^5 + (2n^2 - 4n^2\mu)x^4 + (n^2 - l^2n^2 - 6n^2\mu + 6n^2\mu^2)x^3 + (-1 + \mu - 2l\mu - 2n^2\mu + 2l^2n^2\mu + 6n^2\mu^2 - 4n^2\mu^3)x^2 + (-2 + 4\mu - 4l\mu^2 + n^2\mu^2 - l^2n^2\mu^2 - 2n^2\mu^3 + n^2\mu^4)x + (-1 + l^2 + 3\mu - l^2\mu - 3\mu^2 + \mu^3 - 2l\mu^3) = 0$$

Since $\mu \ll 1$, therefore neglecting second and higher powers of μ , we then get

$$n^2 x^5 + (2n^2 - 4n^2\mu)x^4 + (n^2 - l^2n^2 - 6n^2\mu)x^3 + (-1 + \mu - 2l\mu - 2n^2\mu + 2l^2n^2\mu)x^2 + (-2 + 4\mu)x + (-1 + l^2 + 3\mu - l^2\mu) = 0 \tag{10}$$

The Equation (10) is a fifth degree equation in x , depending upon μ and l . On solving it for various values of μ and l we get only three real solutions (Table-1).

Table 1: Location of Collinear Libration Points for different values of μ

l	$\mu = 0.001$			l	$\mu = 0.2$		
	$L_1(x)$	$L_2(x)$	$L_3(x)$		$L_1(x)$	$L_2(x)$	$L_3(x)$
0.1	-1.09805	-0.899703	1.7044	0.1	-0.93833	-0.522241	1.74463
0.2	-1.19816	-0.799525	1.33915	0.2	-0.95796	-0.49415	1.42178
0.3	-1.29831	-0.699398	1.14929	0.3	-1.04426	-0.416645	1.25748
0.4	-1.39846	-0.599297	1.0168	0.4	-1.16094	-0.31838	1.14502
0.5	-1.49859	-0.499213	0.908999	0.5	-1.2836	-0.212196	1.05542
0.6	-1.59871	-0.399141	0.811431	0.6	-1.40355	-0.1064	0.976527
0.7	-1.6988	-0.299082	0.71469	0.7	-1.51942	-0.006248	0.901514
0.8	-1.79888	-0.199037	0.608747	0.8	-1.63176	-0.081977	0.825281
0.9	-1.89895	-0.0990084	0.473158	0.9	-1.74139	0.149947	0.742725
l	$\mu = 0.01$			l	$\mu = 0.3$		
	$L_1(x)$	$L_2(x)$	$L_3(x)$		$L_1(x)$	$L_2(x)$	$L_3(x)$

0.1	-1.08069	-0.896725	1.70572	0.1	-0.93286	-0.136033	1.77949
0.2	-1.18182	-0.79502	1.34171	0.2	-0.92489	-0.103725	1.49847
0.3	-1.28329	-0.693783	1.15251	0.3	-0.97893	-0.050034	1.36244
0.4	-1.38477	-0.592797	1.02047	0.4	-1.08499	0.146172	1.2739
0.5	-1.4861	-0.491968	0.913033	0.5	-1.21239	0.0800845	1.20735
0.6	-1.58724	-0.391261	0.815769	0.6	-1.33958	0.139873	1.15291
0.7	-1.68818	-0.290673	0.719307	0.7	-1.46124	0.189728	1.10609
0.8	-1.78897	-0.190224	0.613642	0.8	-1.57774	0.224378	1.06493
0.9	-1.88961	-0.0899397	0.478382	0.9	-1.6903	0.230527	1.02915
	$\mu = 0.1$				$\mu = 0.4$		
l	$L_1(x)$	$L_2(x)$	$L_3(x)$	l	$L_1(x)$	$L_2(x)$	$L_3(x)$
0.1	-0.962095	-0.797197	1.72107	0.1	-0.93055	0.303982	1.8346
0.2	-1.04223	-0.714723	1.37237	0.2	-0.91007	0.293967	1.62143
0.3	-1.15074	-0.611593	1.19182	0.3	-0.9414	0.294549	1.52937
0.4	-1.26412	-0.505455	1.06614	0.4	-1.03066	0.300534	1.47526
0.5	-1.37692	-0.398739	0.964105	0.5	-1.15754	0.308129	1.43865
0.6	-1.48771	-0.292251	0.871966	0.6	-1.29002	0.314046	1.41205
0.7	-1.59643	-0.186675	0.780966	0.7	-1.41637	0.314655	1.39219
0.8	-1.70341	-0.0828416	0.682142	0.8	-1.53614	0.304372	1.37758
0.9	-1.80901	0.0178262	0.558601	0.9	-1.6509	0.269734	1.36758

	$\mu = 0.5$		
l	$L_1(x)$	$L_2(x)$	$L_3(x)$
0.1	-0.929289	0.705188	1.92753
0.2	-0.902033	0.586006	1.81294
0.3	-0.918976	0.519033	1.777193
0.4	-0.992192	0.474638	1.75099
0.5	-1.11481	0.441300	1.73882
0.6	-1.25086	0.412615	1.73163
0.7	-1.38102	0.38347	1.72787
0.8	-1.50342	0.347494	1.72685
0.9	-1.61986	0.290733	1.72828

Fig. 4: l verses $L_1(x)$

Fig. 5: l verses $L_2(x)$

Fig. 6: l versus $L_3(x)$

It is clear from Table-1, there exist three collinear libration points L_1 , L_2 and L_3 . The first libration point L_1 lies at the left of M , L_2 lies between M and m_1 and L_3 lies at the right of m_1 . This is also observed that as the value of length parameter l increases, the first libration point L_1 goes away from the centre of mass (Fig. 4), the second and third libration points L_2 and L_3 come toward the centre of mass as l increases for $0 \leq \mu \leq \frac{1}{2}$ (Fig. 5 and Fig. 6).

3.2 Non-collinear Libration Points

For the non-collinear libration points $y \neq 0$, therefore Equations (7) and (8) become

$$n^2 x - \frac{1-\mu}{r_1^3} (x-\mu) - \frac{4\mu l}{(r+r')^2 - 4l^2} \left(\frac{x+1-\mu+l}{r} + \frac{x+1-\mu-l}{r'} \right) = 0, \tag{11}$$

and

$$n^2 - \frac{1-\mu}{r_1^3} - \frac{4\mu l}{(r+r')^2 - 4l^2} \left(\frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{r'} \right) = 0. \tag{12}$$

On eliminating r_1 from the Equations (11) and (12), we get

$$n^2 - \frac{4l}{(r+r')^2 - 4l^2} \left(\frac{1+l}{r} + \frac{1-l}{r'} \right) = 0. \tag{13}$$

The solution of Equation (13) is $r = r' = 1$. Thus the co-ordinates of the non-collinear libration points $L_4, 5$ are $(\mu-1, \pm \sqrt{1-l^2})$.

Since $r = r' = 1$, therefore $r_1 = \left(\frac{1-l^2}{2l}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}}$.

In the classical case of the restricted three body problem, the non-collinear libration points $L_{4,5}$ form an equilateral triangle with the primaries but in our case the non-collinear libration points $L_{4,5}$ form an isosceles triangle with the smaller primary M of length $2l$ (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7: Location of the Non-Collinear Libration Points $L_{4,5}$

4. Stability of Libration Points

The Equations of the motion of the infinitesimal mass are

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{x} - 2n\dot{y} &= \Omega_x \\ \ddot{y} + 2n\dot{x} &= \Omega_y \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Let the co-ordinates of the Libration-point be (x, y) . We give small displacement (α, β) to (x, y) . The equations of motion become

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{\alpha} - 2n\dot{\beta} &= \Omega_x(x + \alpha, y + \beta) \\ \ddot{\beta} + 2n\dot{\alpha} &= \Omega_y(x + \alpha, y + \beta) \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

Therefore, the Equations (14) become

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{\alpha} - 2n\dot{\beta} &= \alpha \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx} + \beta \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xy} \\ \ddot{\beta} + 2n\dot{\alpha} &= \alpha \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yx} + \beta \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy} \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

where the partial derivatives are to be calculated at the Libration-point under consideration.

The characteristic Equation of (16) is given by

$$\lambda^4 + (4n^2 - \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx} - \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy})\lambda^2 + \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx}\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy} - (\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xy})^2 = 0 \tag{17}$$

which is a fourth degree equation in λ .

The Libration-point (x, y) is stable if all the four roots of the Equation (17) are pure imaginary.

On differentiating the Equation (7) with respect to x and y , we get

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{xx} = n^2 + \frac{3(1-\mu)(x-\mu)^2}{r_1^5} - \frac{(1-\mu)}{r_1^3} + \frac{8\mu l(r+r')}{[(r+r')^2 - 4l^2]^2} \left(\frac{x+1-\mu+l}{r} + \frac{x+1-\mu-l}{r'} \right)^2 \\ - \frac{4\mu l}{(r+r')^2 - 4l^2} \left(\frac{r^2 - (x+1-\mu+l)^2}{r^3} + \frac{r'^2 - (x+1-\mu-l)^2}{r'^3} \right), \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{xy} = \frac{3(1-\mu)(x-\mu)y}{r_1^5} + \frac{8\mu l(r+r')y}{[(r+r')^2 - 4l^2]^2} \left(\frac{x+1-\mu+l}{r} + \frac{x+1-\mu-l}{r'} \right) \left(\frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{r'} \right) \\ + \frac{4\mu l y}{(r+r')^2 - 4l^2} \left(\frac{x+1-\mu+l}{r^3} + \frac{x+1-\mu-l}{r'^3} \right), \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

On differentiating the Equation (8) with respect to y , we get

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{yy} = n^2 - \frac{(1-\mu)}{r_1^3} - \frac{4\mu l y}{(r+r')^2 - 4l^2} \left(\frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{r'} \right) + \frac{3(1-\mu)}{r_1^5} y^2 + \frac{4\mu l y^2}{(r+r')^2 - 4l^2} \left(\frac{1}{r^3} + \frac{1}{r'^3} \right) \\ + \frac{8\mu l y^2 (r+r')}{[(r+r')^2 - 4l^2]^2} \left(\frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{r'} \right)^2. \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

4.1 Stability of the Non-collinear Libration point L_4

The co-ordinates of the non-collinear libration point L_4 is $(\mu-1, \sqrt{1-l^2})$. Since $n = 1$ for $l = 0.4$ therefore at the Libration point L_4 the values of $\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx}$, $\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xy}$ and $\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy}$ are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx} &= 2.81332 - 2.61332\mu, \\ \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xy} &= -2.61861(1-\mu), \\ \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy} &= 2.37081 - 0.491301\mu. \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{21}$$

Hence, the characteristic Equation (17) becomes

$$\lambda^4 + (-1.18413 + 3.10462\mu)\lambda^2 - 0.187286 + 6.1364\mu - 5.57321\mu^2 = 0 \tag{22}$$

Let $\lambda^2 = \Lambda$, therefore

$$\Lambda^2 + (-1.18413 + 3.10462\mu)\Lambda - 0.187286 + 6.1364\mu - 5.57321\mu^2 = 0 \tag{23}$$

The solution of the Equation (23) is

$$\Lambda_{1,2} = 0.592067 - 1.55231\mu \pm 0.5\sqrt{2.15132 - 31.8982\mu + 31.9315\mu^2} \tag{24}$$

The roots of the characteristic Equation (22) i.e. $\lambda_{1,2} = \pm\sqrt{\Lambda_1}$ and $\lambda_{3,4} = \pm\sqrt{\Lambda_2}$ will be pure imaginary if Λ_1 and Λ_2 are negative. From the Equation (24) it is clear that Λ_1 and Λ_2 will be negative if

$$0.592067 - 1.55231\mu < 0$$

$$\text{and } 2.15132 - 31.8982\mu + 31.9315\mu^2 < 0$$

The above two conditions are satisfied for $\mu = 0.381410285\dots$. Hence for $\mu = 0.381410285\dots$ the non-collinear libration points $L_{4,5}$ are stable.

4.2 Stability of the collinear libration points

At the collinear libration points, $y = 0$, therefore at $L_1(x, 0)$, Ω_{xx} , Ω_{xy} and Ω_{yy} becomes,

$$\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xx} = n^2 + \frac{2(1-\mu)}{(x_i - \mu)^3} + \frac{4\mu l(x_i + 1 - \mu)}{[(x_i + 1 - \mu)^2 - l^2]^2},$$

$$\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{xy} = 0,$$

$$\overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{yy} = n^2 - \frac{1-\mu}{(x_i - \mu)^3}.$$

where $i = 1, 2, 3$.

The roots of the characteristic Equation (17) are given as follows -

Table 2: Stability of L_1 for $\mu=0.001$

l	$L_1(x)$	$\lambda_{1,2}$	$\lambda_{3,4}$
0.1	-1.09805	± 0.975246	$\pm 33.3663i$
0.2	-1.19816	± 0.996598	$\pm 37.709i$
0.3	-1.29831	± 1.05483	$\pm 45.8764i$
0.4	-1.39846	± 1.14688	$\pm 58.5929i$
0.5	-1.49859	± 1.27612	$\pm 77.1498i$
0.6	-1.59871	± 1.45544	$\pm 109.056i$
0.7	-1.6988	± 1.71698	$\pm 158.119i$
0.8	-1.79888	± 2.14837	$\pm 263.523i$
0.9	-1.89895	± 3.10149	$\pm 632.451i$

Table 3: Stability of L_1 for $\mu=0.01$

l	$L_1(x)$	$\lambda_{1,2}$	$\lambda_{3,4}$
0.1	-1.08069	± 0.965825	$\pm 10.8715i$
0.2	-1.18182	± 0.987743	$\pm 12.4141i$
0.3	-1.28329	± 1.04755	$\pm 15.0436i$
0.4	-1.38477	± 1.14150	$\pm 19.2182i$
0.5	-1.4861	± 1.27450	$\pm 25.7041i$
0.6	-1.58724	± 1.45311	$\pm 36.2677i$
0.7	-1.68818	± 1.71562	$\pm 54.9601i$
0.8	-1.78897	± 2.14768	$\pm 97.0868i$
0.9	-1.88961	± 3.10121	$\pm 256.400i$

Table 4: Stability of L_1 for $\mu=0.1$

l	$L_1(x)$	$\lambda_{1,2}$	$\lambda_{3,4}$
0.1	-0.962095	± 0.948817	$\pm 8.42859i$
0.2	-1.04223	± 0.950419	$\pm 5.81238i$
0.3	-1.15074	± 1.01111	$\pm 6.71154i$
0.4	-1.26412	± 1.11516	$\pm 9.01108i$
0.5	-1.37692	± 1.25665	$\pm 13.8136i$
0.6	-1.48771	± 1.44474	$\pm 25.7789i$
0.7	-1.59643	± 1.71113	$\pm 88.5881i$
0.8	-1.70341	± 2.14377	$\pm 92.7345i$
0.9	-1.80901	± 3.09386	$\pm 35.0222i$

Table 5: Stability of L_1 for $\mu=0.2$

l	$L_1(x)$	$\lambda_{1,2}$	$\lambda_{3,4}$
0.1	-0.93833	± 0.850197	$\pm 11.7247i$
0.2	-0.95796	± 0.948724	$\pm 10.7789i$
0.3	-1.04426	± 1.00610	$\pm 8.23441i$
0.4	-1.16094	± 1.1101	$\pm 11.5926i$
0.5	-1.2836	± 1.25295	$\pm 27.323i$
0.6	-1.40355	± 1.43823	$\pm 125.985i$
0.7	-1.51942	± 1.69728	$\pm 23.0599i$
0.8	-1.63176	± 2.1176	$\pm 14.0686i$
0.9	-1.74139	± 3.04392	$\pm 10.541i$

Table 6: Stability of L_1 for $\mu=0.3$

l	$L_1(x)$	$\lambda_{1,2}$	$\lambda_{3,4}$
0.1	-0.93286	± 0.67544	$\pm 4.32591i$
0.2	-0.92489	± 0.889394	$\pm 22.0655i$
0.3	-0.97893	± 0.994041	$\pm 26.0551i$
0.4	-1.08499	± 1.10101	$\pm 36.5327i$
0.5	-1.21239	± 1.23796	$\pm 44.2382i$
0.6	-1.33958	± 1.41147	$\pm 13.9178i$
0.7	-1.46124	± 1.65426	$\pm 9.01259i$
0.8	-1.57774	± 2.05184	$\pm 6.99717i$
0.9	-1.6903	± 2.93371	$\pm 5.51865i$

Table 7: Stability of L_1 for $\mu=0.4$

l	$L_1(x)$	$\lambda_{1,2}$	$\lambda_{3,4}$
0.1	-0.93055	± 0.522579	$\pm 3.08081i$
0.2	-0.91007	± 0.779742	$\pm 5.95986i$
0.3	-0.9414	± 0.944781	$\pm 15.3697i$
0.4	-1.03066	± 1.07075	$\pm 20.6974i$
0.5	-1.15754	± 1.20181	$\pm 11.1083i$
0.6	-1.29002	± 1.35992	$\pm 7.16548i$
0.7	-1.41637	± 1.5823	$\pm 5.52064i$
0.8	-1.53614	± 1.94986	$\pm 4.52160i$
0.9	-1.6509	± 2.75845	$\pm 3.19256i$

Table 8: Stability of L_1 for $\mu=0.5$

l	$L_1(x)$	$\lambda_{1,2}$	$\lambda_{3,4}$
0.1	-0.929289	± 0.404823	$\pm 2.59952i$
0.2	-0.902033	± 0.664299	$\pm 3.82878i$
0.3	-0.918976	± 0.865052	$\pm 6.16116i$
0.4	-0.992192	± 1.016060	$\pm 7.84078i$
0.5	-1.11481	± 1.41584	$\pm 6.34784i$
0.6	-1.25086	± 1.41076	$\pm 47.7664i$
0.7	-1.38102	± 1.66755	$\pm 13.9442i$
0.8	-1.50342	± 2.07209	$\pm 8.68753i$
0.9	-1.61986	± 2.75845	$\pm 1.16124i$

The nature of the roots in above Table (2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8) shows that the collinear libration point L_1 is unstable for all values of $0 \leq \mu \leq \frac{1}{2}$ and $0 < l < 1$. Similarly the other collinear libration points L_2 and L_3 are also unstable in $0 \leq \mu \leq \frac{1}{2}$ and $0 < l < 1$.

5. Conclusion:

In this paper we have studied the existence and stability of the libration points in the restricted three-body problem when one of the primaries is a uniform rod. This is observed that there exist three collinear libration points L_i ($i= 1, 2, 3$), the first libration point L_1 lies at the left of M , L_2 lies between M and m_1 and L_3 lies the right of m_1 . This is also observed that as the value of mass parameter μ and length of the rod l increases the first Libration point L_1 and the third libration point L_3 go away from the center of mass and the second Libration point L_2 come towards the centre of mass as μ increases and two non-collinear libration points $L_{4,5}$ forming an isosceles triangle with the smaller primary M of length $2l$. This is also observed that non-collinear $L_{4,5}$ are stable for a critical value of mass parameter $\mu_c = 0.381410285\dots$ while the collinear libration points L_i ($i= 1, 2, 3$) are unstable in $0 \leq \mu \leq \frac{1}{2}$ and $0 < l < 1$.

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